

COMMUNICATION BETWEEN SUPPLIERS OF GOODS, SERVICES AND CONSUMERS IN THE FIELD OF ELECTRONIC COMMERCE IN TERMS OF CONSUMER PROTECTION

Author(s)*: Mircea Dan RADU
Position: PhD Student
University: Technical University of Cluj-Napoca
Deputy Chief Commissioner at the Regional Commissioner for Consumer Protection North West
Region Cluj
Address: Cluj-Napoca, Memorandumului Str., No. 28, Romania
Email: mircea.radu.cjpc@gmail.com

Abstract

In recent years, e-commerce has gained considerable momentum, being present in the daily lives of most active people, young people, but viewed with great interest and by the elderly but eager to be up to date, especially in the current context of global trade rules. The new trade measures imposed by the state in the world in the context of COVID-19, ensure a greater visibility but also vulnerability of electronic commerce, which imposes a series of new rules, necessary to be adopted by economic agents which invariably leads to the application of almost unitary international of the new requirements. The paper analyzes the way in which the Romanian consumer adapts to the international conditions of electronic commerce and to what extent he has an identical or almost identical behavior with the international consumer.

Purpose – *The role of this paper is to highlight in the spirit of this dynamic of the evolution of e-commerce, the optimal forms of communication between the parties involved so that the consumer is satisfied with the result of the process of purchasing goods and services through the online system and the selling company can develop communication, new, secure and reliable systems for presenting and selling products and services, while adapting to new consumer requirements.*

Methodology/approach - *Relevant statistical data are collected and centralized for the two types of trade, classic and online, data related to three years, useful for forming a clear but punctual opinion on the state we are in, both in relation to the domestic and international market and to what extent can communication improve this sector.*

Findings – *The centralization of the data found that in terms of online commerce, consumers in the NW region of Romania face the same types of problems as consumers in other states, which is highlighted by comparison with international statistics published by various institutions approved in the field of electronic commerce. and we are also willing to buy and spend more money on online transactions just like consumers in other countries.*

Research limitations/implications – *In the context of globalization, the management of the relationship between suppliers and consumers in the field of electronic commerce is an important issue in terms of the current situation in which a special emphasis is placed on online activities both nationally and internationally.*

Practical implications - *It was analyzed in terms of data collected and centralized at the level of consumer protection Cluj the reasons why some consumers choose to buy products and services online compared to consumers in other countries, according to data taken from international statistics published online*

Originality/value - *Acquisition of a relevant number of data from the Cluj consumer protection institution, which in fact reflects the regional, maybe even national, trend. The data were collected with the agreement of the management of the above-mentioned institution.*

Key words: *e-commerce, communication, consumer protection.*

INTRODUCTION

The current outbreak of COVID-19 has led to a major disruption to people's daily lives, work and travel, while affecting the way they purchase goods and services in the traditional system through direct sales. Many European companies have thus moved their activity mainly online, trying to adapt to the new conditions, which has invariably led to the adoption of relatively uniform e-commerce procedures. It is a considerable effort by economic operators to adapt to a type of global trade in the online environment, given that European bodies anticipate a severe crisis on the European economy. (Europe, 2020)

In an extremely short period of time, COVID-19 has highlighted how much economic power has shifted to the customer and how this change has widened the gap between those who are in the field of online commerce and those who are not. All companies, not just those in Europe, are now more aware than ever that e-commerce is essential and that they need well-defined digital strategies. (KPMG, 2020)

The major interest in online commerce is highlighted by several international statistics for 2020 (Mohsin, 2020): 1,8 billion people shop online, aproape 50% of consumers shop more on mobile than in-store, because of the coronavirus 42% of the US population bought groceries online in March 2020, nearly double the 22% in 2018.

This paper is important by the way the Romanian consumer is analyzed in comparison with the consumer from other states using the same analysis parameters.

We analyze through the collected data whether the consumer behavior in the NW region of Romania, a representative area for trade and consumption throughout the country, is comparable to the behavior of international consumers.

Taking into account this aspect, the behavioral changes of the international economic agents will affect to the same extent both the consumer from the country where the enterprise originates and the rest of the world and to the same extent the Romanian consumer, the borders not existing in online trade.

The paper is current in terms of data collected and centralized in the last three years, data provided by the consumer protection institution Cluj which is responsible for six counties in NW Romania and also capitalizes on essential data on the perception, understanding and usefulness of e-commerce in the current global context.

Summarizing the data collected, it was found that the problems highlighted by the Romanian consumer are largely identical to those reported in various publications and international reports on consumers in other countries, not just European.

Also, from the analysis of these data as well as from the cited publications it appears that through a good communication of the factors involved in the online trade almost all the impediments of this type of commercial activity can be solved, taking into account the globalization of the trade act. The usefulness of the chosen topic also emerges from the title of the paper due to the extremely important role that communication has in the relationship between the consumer, the company and the authorities.

BACKGROUND

The main topics used in this paper on which the research was built are e-commerce and communication.

Since the 2000s, the emphasis has been on e-commerce communication, (Lee, Corbitt, & Kong, 2000) examines the typology of e-commerce in terms of communication and uses this typology to examine the role and nature of the relationship created in the practice of e-commerce.

Effective communication between these parties will lead to positive financial results for the company.

The influencers described in "What e-commerce communication strategy should you adopt in 2019" (Herpin, 2018) are people who are part of the e-commerce landscape and who motivate their audience through a specific form of communication.

Communication formats according to the paper „*Building an Agile Communications Strategy*” (Oracle Corporation, 2014) they can include several types, such as those commonly used to print specific customer access documents, interactive formats, and responsive formats that allow for a logical view of the content.

Factors described according to (Baubonienė & Gulevičiūtė, 2015) leading to the decision to shop online and develop an understanding of the factors that influence online shopping by consumers can be divided into those that offer benefits, namely security, fast delivery, comparable price, comfort, cheaper prices and a range wider and on the other hand the disadvantages.

Disadvantages can easily turn into advantages if we use effective communication through which the consumer understands the benefits of online commerce. The role of selling companies is to use all communication strategies in such a way that the consumer notices the advantages of this type of online commerce compared to traditional commerce.

Communication between suppliers of goods or services and consumers is of major interest in the context of the exponential growth of the type of trade defined as "e-commerce", "online commerce" or the international language "e-commerce".

This topic on e-commerce communication in all its forms can be topical and requires careful consideration due to the existence of an imbalance between the participants. Thus, companies operating in the field of online commerce have the economic power that allows them to apply working methods beneficial to their financial interests often using aggressive promotion techniques, while on the other hand the consumer presents himself as a vulnerable and destitute person. The levers needed to balance this balance.

The success of the business depends on the communication between employees and employer, owner and manager, manager and employees, salespeople and customers, etc. (Kumbhar, 2014).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The paper is based on research literature and based on a synthesis of centralized data related to the last three years, used with approval in this research. At the same time, bibliographic research highlights the importance of communication techniques used by stakeholders.

Thus, the comparison by which the behavior of the Romanian consumer is analyzed compared to the behavior of the international consumer is based on the bibliographic research using the specialized literature that identifies the problems of the international consumer as well as various statistical data by which the purchasing decisions are analyzed. and services and on the other hand a centralization of some data close as content and significance of those highlighted in research literature, data that are collected from the institution of consumer protection Cluj and subsequently centralized.

The main reasons that determine buyers to choose a certain type of trade, respectively online or offline, and on the other hand the reasons for dissatisfaction of both types of buyers are identified.

Communication between suppliers of goods, services and consumers in the field of e-commerce in terms of consumer protection is analyzed through a research that uses centralized data of the consumer protection authority, collected and centralized over 3 years, respectively 2017, 2018, 2019 and partly 2020. It is thus verified to what extent an efficient communication between the factors involved in solving some management problems leads to a favorable solution for the consumer in the shortest possible time.

In terms of data collected and centralized for the years mentioned resulted a large but relatively constant number of complaints and complaints from consumers addressed to economic operators for violation of rights, respectively 3715 in 2017, 3809 in 2018, 3067 in 2019 and 608 in the first 2 months of year 2020.

From the interpretation of the data, it must be clear whether the reasons that lead buyers to buy products and services online or directly from stores as well as the reasons for dissatisfaction associated with both types of trade, but also ways to improve communication that could reduce dissatisfaction of both categories. Romanian consumers, are also found in the results present in world statistics.

RESEARCH FINDING

After interpreting the graphs resulting from the centralization of the data, a comparison was made with the data resulting internationally, presented in several papers. This information, which refers to the communication present in e-commerce and the traditional one at international level, is important to understand what will be the next steps in the future, taking into account the ascending evolution of e-commerce. They are useful in formulating conclusions that can lead to improved communication between the factors involved in the process of purchasing products and services online, described above.

The description of commercially non-compliant facts by the consumer is essential in centralizing the initial data, as shown in *Figure 1*.

Figure 1. Consumer complaints broken down by categories registered for consumer protection Cluj, before their actual research, seen through the prism of consumers in 2017, 2018, 2019 and partially 2020

By comparison, reasons for international consumers, other than those in Romania, to buy from stores, ie purchased offline at the expense of online purchases, according to (KPMG Report, 2017) the following are in descending order: I want to see or touch the product, I want to try, delivery time is too long, purchase costs are too high, I like the shopping experience, I will go shopping anyway, I want to check through my own senses the authenticity of the product, the form of return of the goods is too complicated I do not trust online commerce and lastly, is the desire to actually talk to a seller.

The data resulting from the centralization of statistical data at the level of the consumer protection institution, the situations are similar to those present in statistics performed at the international level. Thus, the annual global report on online consumers in 2017, prepared by KPMG and presented in the paper, states eloquent data based on an online survey applied to 18,430 consumers living in more than 50 countries aged between 15 and 70 years old, and who have purchased at least one consumer product online in the last 12 months. According to this report, as in Figure 1, the reasons why shoppers choose classic stores over online ones are shown. The desire to touch or see the product, to try it, to see if it

looks different, are the most chosen options by international consumers followed by the statement that the delivery time in the online case is long, which creates a disadvantage for the customer.

Thus, the reasons and factors for which Romanian consumers choose to purchase products or services directly from stores at the expense of online purchases are similar to those in the international statistics.

However, taking into account the change produced by COVID 19 in the entire act of trade, online commerce is clearly detached from the classic trade, almost all economic agents who understood the phenomenon and did not cling to the past, took the step and began to offer services and in the digital sphere.

This has invariably led to deficiencies in the act of electronic commerce, an aspect reported by all consumers regardless of the country where they purchase products or services.

It should be noted that 88% of customers consider that highlighting the details of the products to be purchased are crucial for making an online purchasing decision. (Ouellette, 2020), aspect also found in the decisions of the Romanian buyer.

As consumers continue to change their types of online shopping (KPMG Report, 2017), Retailers who understand the factors that motivate them to shop online or in-store will be better positioned to create sales-specific communication channels that meet the needs and preferences of their customers.

Among the reasons described in the report based on which customers choose online stores, we mention in descending order of interest: the ability to buy 24/7, the ability to compare prices, selling online means a competitive price, save time, convenience of purchase, great variety of products, all in one place, the products I am interested in are not found in my area of residence,

Another study (Fang, Wen, George , & Prybutok, 2016) conducted on 651 online shoppers, empirical evidence shows that both age and gender can affect the intention to buy online in terms of the quality of the product or service, respectively the quality of communication, as well. These values are also found in the case of consumption in Romania, a fact highlighted by the centralized data on consumer protection in the NV Cluj Region.

The Romanian consumer finds himself with the same types of problems among international consumers according to the data centralized at international level in the paper (Hunter & Riefa, 2017) respectively: non-delivery of purchased products, long delivery time, questionable quality of purchased product, delivered product that does not match the order, defective delivered product, lack of nearby service for repair, higher final costs than initial, impossibility to return the product and non-receipt of the amount paid and lack of information on the seller's data.

Understanding the online phenomenon is essential for the future of this type of business. The caution and vigilance regarding what follows leads us to evaluate much better the decisions to purchase products or services online, which led to a decrease of about 9% in transactions in May and June of this year. (Paul, 2020). By comparison, we can say based on the centralized data that the Romanian consumer is also in this category, of those who pay attention to the money paid to achieve an economy, taking into account the current context.

CONCLUSIONS

The interpretation of the data also shows that not all non-compliant aspects of traders are reported by consumers, time playing an important role and the communication of disturbing or unrealistic aspects of the act of trade are overlooked by consumers. The small financial inconvenience for the consumer determines him to accept the loss, a fact that the selling companies take advantage of financially.

Given that in this period deeply marked by restrictions on the purchase of products and services offline due to COVID-19, merchants who sell products online take full advantage of the major interest of consumers in this way of shopping, which leads, in the medium or long term, to a degradation of the quality of the online trade act, a fact highlighted by the increase in the number of complaints and the lack of interest in communicating with the customer.

The issues presented lead to the conclusion that consumers are increasingly willing to buy more products from all categories online and spend more money on online transactions while respecting in principle the same predominant factors regarding the decision to buy or not a product or a service, both international and local.

Thus, the results of data centralization in the institution of consumer protection Cluj fits almost perfectly on the international model, in the sense that this trend towards often aggressive or misleading communication from many selling companies to attract more customers, regardless of the subsequent loss of customers is manifested not only in the Cluj region but also internationally.

It is gratifying that since the Romanian consumer falls into the same pattern as the international consumer, we will have to adopt the same strategies of the big players in the online market under the careful regulation of the profile bodies specific to each community.

Highlighting and applying a common strategy regulated in the e-commerce market without taking into account borders, shows the direction we are heading, respectively a globalization of these commercial activities carried out by almost all companies and communication is the key to implementing these mechanisms successfully.

References

Baubonienė, Ž., & Gulevičiūtė, G.

2015

E-COMMERCE FACTORS INFLUENCING CONSUMERS' ONLINE SHOPPING DECISION, Vol 5(1), p. 74–81, ISSN 2029-7564 (online). Retrieved from /www3.mruni.eu: <https://www3.mruni.eu/ojs/social-technologies/article/view/4295/4067>

Europe, E.

2020

Learn more about the situation in Europe regarding e-commerce and the Coronavirus. Retrieved from www.ecommerce-europe.eu/coronavirus: <https://www.ecommerce-europe.eu/coronavirus-ecommerce-info-center/>

Fang, J., Wen, C., George, B., & Prybutok, V.

2016

CONSUMER HETEROGENEITY, PERCEIVED VALUE, AND REPURCHASE DECISION-MAKING IN ONLINE SHOPPING: THE ROLE OF GENDER, AGE, AND SHOPPING MOTIVES, *Journal of Electronic Commerce Research*, VOL 17, NO 2. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/299559872_Consumer_Heterogeneity_Perceived_Value_and_Repurchase_Decision-Making_in_Online_Shopping_The_Role_of_Gender_Age_and_Shopping_Motives: <http://web.csulb.edu/journals/jecr/issues/20162/Paper2.pdf>

Herpin, T.

2018

WHAT E-COMMERCE COMMUNICATION STRATEGY SHOULD YOU ADOPT IN 2019 ? Retrieved from /www.ecommerce-nation.com: <https://www.ecommerce-nation.com/e-commerce-communication-strategy-adopt/>

Hunter, J., & Riefa, C.

2017

The challenge of protecting EU consumers in global online markets. Retrieved from www.vzbv.de: https://www.vzbv.de/sites/default/files/downloads/2017/11/08/17-11-08_brochure-vzbv-beuc-lr3.pdf

KPMG

2020

COVID-19 and the rise of e-commerce. Retrieved from advisory.kpmg.us/: <https://advisory.kpmg.us/events/webcast-homepage/2020/covid-19-and-rise-of-ecommerce.html>

KPMG Report

2017

The truth about online consumers, 2017 Global Online Consumer Report, ©2017 KPMG International Cooperative. Retrieved from www.kpmg.com: <https://assets.kpmg/content/dam/kpmg/xx/pdf/2017/01/the-truth-about-online-consumers.pdf>

Kumbhar, V.

2014

Business Communications M. A. Part – II ECONOMICS , Group – C1 – Optional Paper – XXIV , Unit No. 8. Retrieved from /www.researchgate.net:

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/235938453_Business_Communication

Lee, C., Corbitt, B., & Kong, W.-C.

2000

Stakeholder Relationships and Electronic Commerce Differentiation. Retrieved from

<http://www.pacis-net.org/file/2000/100-114.pdf>: <http://www.pacis-net.org>

Mohsin, M.

2020

10 Online Shopping Statistics You Need to Know in 2020. Retrieved from <https://www.oberlo.com/>:

<https://www.oberlo.com/blog/online-shopping-statistics>

Oracle Corporation

2014

Building an Agile Communications Strategy. Retrieved from <http://www.oracle.com>:

<http://www.oracle.com/us/industries/financial-services/insurance-documaker-agile-wp-1983675.pdf>

Ouellette, C.

2020

Online Shopping Statistics for 2020. Retrieved from <https://optinmonster.com/>:

<https://optinmonster.com/online-shopping-statistics/>

Paul, S.

2020

Online shopping still booming, but starting to drop as consumers tentatively step out. Retrieved from

<https://internetretailing.net/covid-19>: <https://internetretailing.net/covid-19/covid-19/online-shopping-still-booming-but-starting-to-drop-as-consumers-tentatively-step-out-21573>

Verčič, D., Moreno, Á., & Verhoeven, P.

2018

EUROPEAN COMMUNICATION MONITOR 2018, HOW INFORMATION PROVISION CREATES CORPORATE VALUE , European Communication Summit. Retrieved from

www.communicationmonitor.eu: http://www.communicationmonitor.eu/wp-content/uploads/European-Communication-Monitor-2018-ECM18-Presentation_Berlin_13_06_2018_Summit.pdf